

BASIC CONCEPTS OF SOFT SKILLS FOR SURGICAL TEAMS

SITUATION AWARENESS

Definition: Perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and a projection of their status in the near future.

Key Concepts

- Situation awareness in the OR should be shared across the team, in order to assure a safe and efficient surgical performance for the patient.
- The situation awareness is held both by human and non-human agents, with different views on the same scene that might be compensated.
- Inattentional blindness emphasizes the importance of focused attention.
- Informational, environmental, personal and organisational influences might negatively affect the situation awareness.
- The use of checklists, minimizing interruptions, resume the task some steps before, promote communication, and time management could enhance situation awareness.

Learning Objectives

- To differentiate individual situation awareness from shared situations awareness.
- To identify the three levels of situation awareness.
- To recognize the four domains of situation awareness.

Evaluation

- Identify moments within a succession of events where situation awareness might be compromised.
- Select options that result in a better shared situation awareness (assessment checklist).

DECISION MAKING

Definition: Selection of a course of action from among two or more possible alternatives in order to arrive at a solution for a given problem.

Key Concepts

- The decision making process consists of three main parts: situation assessment, taking appropriate actions and re-evaluating the result.
- It has four principal models: recognition-primed (intuitive), rule-based, analytical and creative
- Decision making technique is based on the decision maker's previous experience.
- The type of the decision strategy is determined by the available time and the degree of the risk. In case of emergency and high risk, the decision maker uses fast intuitive or rule-based decision strategies.
- Hurry and stressful environment, age, individual differences, belief in personal relevance, and commitment, influence what choices made.
- Positive decisions increase satisfactory, which help making decisions quickly and with ease.

Learning Objectives

- To differentiate decision making techniques.
- To acquire new decision-making techniques.
- To recognize your own decision making technique.
- To develop communication skills under pressure.
- To improve information gathering skills.

Evaluation

- Select the best way for gathering information.
- Identify the process of our decisions, and the influencing factors.
- Select options that may result the best decision making strategy (assessment checklist).

TEAMWORK

Learning Objectives

- To recognise the principles and potential of teamwork.
- To define the roles of individual team members.
- To estimate the newly established team functioning.
- To differentiate various types of leadership.
- To establish main indicators for teamwork efficiency evaluation.
- To reconstruct the previous situations and to prevent the mistakes according to the analysis.

Definition: Modern tool in organisations providing interplay, cooperation of individuals and creative solution of tasks (working in functioning teams provides the possibility to eliminate the mistakes and improve the performance).

Key Concepts

- The team is created from a small number of people ideally complementing each other and usually sharing a common goal.
- Belbin's categorisation comprises the cognitive (specialist, innovator and evaluator), affective (coordinator, team worker and resource investigator) and behavioural (shaper, implementer and finisher) roles.
- A precise formulation of the tasks that each role is in charge of is necessary.
- The quality of the individuals influences the team.
- The team members should be emphatic and able to consider current condition and limits of each other.

Evaluation

- Appropriately define a role-based team structure.
- Select proper type of communication under specific circumstances.
- Suitably motivate and coordinate team members in pursuit of reaching the goals.
- Regularly provide feedback to all team members.

COMMUNICATION & INTERACTION

Definition: Exchange of information among the participants and the related context (this comprise using appropriate terminology).

Learning Objectives

- To interpret the communication protocol correctly.
- To follow the guidelines of the role assigned by the protocol.
- To identify the category to which each of the information belongs.
- To use the appropriate communication channels.
- To contribute to the development and improvement of the communication space.

Evaluation

- Relate each role to its function in the communication.
- Follow the established sequence and alter it if necessary.
- Choose the right time to convey a specific message.
- Choose the right way to convey a specific message.
- Alternative proposals and results of its implementation.

Key Concepts

- There are different communication models: linear, interactive and transaction models.
- There are different types of communication: spoken, non-verbal, written and remote communication.
- The communication protocol is a key element in the coordination and planning of communications within the OR.
- There must be some mechanism to ensure that the message has reached the receiver.
- Empathy towards other communicators is especially important in medical communications.

LEADERSHIP

Learning Objectives

- To recognize the different emotions.
- To manage the relationships effectively.
- To delegate tasks, responsibilities and timelines appropriately.
- To manage efficaciously conflict situations.
- To define the roles and responsibilities clearly.
- To utilize appropriate language to communicate effectively.

Definition: Ability to influence others, the capacity to direct, assumed as the key element to define the leader, as the main responsible for the processes of management, planning, implementation and evaluation of an activity.

Key Concepts

- Building trust relations (supports interpersonal relationships established in clinical practice amongst health professionals).
- Create an empowerment-based work environment (promotes improved occupational mental health and work effectiveness / performance).
- Create an environment that supports knowledge development and integration (leads to enhanced personal and professional growth of staff)
- Lead and support change (stimulates team engagement in the change process).
- Balance system complexities (managing competing values and priorities - promotes in the team increased perceptions of their value and self-image).

Evaluation

- Select the right options for an effective leadership process.
- Sequentially choose 2 or more options that promote an effective leadership process.
- Select options that result in adequate leadership processes (assessment checklist).

ASSESSMENT

Within the S4Game scenes presented in the different practical cases, each question/decision node has, in general terms, four answers/options. These represent potential cases and possible reactions of the trainee going through the game. Every answer/option is assessed by particular points according to the appropriateness of the reaction. The final score is calculated from all the given answers. Then the results are converted to a table representing the knowledge of a trainee. He/she will get the feedback.

RESULTS	PERCENTAGE OF POINTS	OUTPUTS AND POSSIBILITIES
A	≥ 90%	Results with justification, possibility to continue to another game or to repeat it again.
B	70% - 89%	Results with justification, possibility to continue to another game or to repeat it again.
C	< 70%	Necessity to repeat the game, THEN results with justification, possibility to continue to another game or to repeat it again.

CASE 3 - INEXPERIENCED TEAM MEMBER REPEATING MISTAKES

Main Skill

Teamwork

Secondary Skill

Communication and Interaction

This practical case focuses on the inter-team communication. The skills how to behave and react are prevalent. Nevertheless, dealing with the external disturbances and other issues should be managed as well. Therefore, these are emphasised in particular situations and decisional actions.

Learning objectives:

- To recognise the principles and potential of teamwork.
- To demonstrate the compensation of the team member's professional insufficiency.
- To recognise the threats of the incompetent behaviour of a team member.
- To practice the team communication skills.
- To use the empathy in the team communication.
- To predict the future malfunction of a team member.
- To judge the consequences of the inefficient teamwork.
- To estimate the newly established team functioning.
- To reconstruct the previous situations in pursuit to prevent the mistakes according to the analysis.

CASE 5 - CLASHES BETWEEN DIFFERENT PROFILES

Main Skill

Leadership

Secondary Skills

Teamwork

Communication and Interaction

In this practical case, it is compulsory to make a decision that will inevitably be based on a shared leadership perspective, assuming communication / interaction as a key role between the different team members as a key role, based on a group work vision in which the different elements contribute to solving this problematic situation.

Learning objectives:

- To demonstrate leadership strategies to manage clashes among different profiles.
- To recognize the different emotions in the surgical team.
- To manage surgical team emotions effectively.
- To demonstrate self-motivation mobilizing the team resources.
- To manage relationships effectively (managing the emotions).
- To utilize appropriate language to communicate effectively.

CASE 6 - MISSING INSTRUMENT

Main Skill

Decision Making

Secondary Skills

Teamwork

Communication and Interaction

This practical case shows that despite all efforts and the best teamwork, unexpected events can occur that require an immediate response. This case study is focusing on the diversity of situation awareness and the presence or absence of a collaborative and supportive environment.

Learning objectives:

- To recognize your own situation awareness level.
- To monitorize unexpected events and their consequences continuously.
- To improve information gathering skills.
- To organize surgical team effectively.
- To develop communication skills under time pressure.
- To evaluate the results of your problem management.

CASE 7 - ABSENCE OF CORRECT STAPLER

Main Skill

Decision Making

Secondary Skills

Communication and Interaction

Leadership

In this practical case, the lack of the correct stapler opens the disjunctive of how to best proceed in the interest of the patient. Other soft skills such as interaction and communication are also present in the practical case.

Learning objectives:

- To anticipate possible errors that might result on patient damage.
- To recognize when a situation might go out of control through the perception of all the elements and people involved.
- To acquire the cognitive resources assisted through checklists to be able to work below the maximum workload to be supported.
- To recognize the consequences that decisions have.

CASE 9 - PROBLEM OF SPREAD ATTENTION

Main Skill

Communication and Interaction

Secondary Skill

Teamwork

In this practical case, the trainee is facing the course of action representing various roles in specific situations. This might cause particular discomfort and not appropriate behaviour in the given context. The spread of knowledge and skills - professional, communication and interpersonal ones - might lead to problematic moments during the game as well as during the real situation.

Learning objectives:

- To recognise the principles and potential of teamwork.
- To practice the team communication skills.
- To use the empathy in the team communication.
- To systemise the course of action.
- To differentiate the priorities of the steps needed.
- To modify own behaviour according to the context.
- To estimate his/her skills to tackle with the current situation.
- To manage the multitasking activities during the intervention and education.
- To reconstruct the previous situations and to prevent the mistakes according to the analysis.